

Research Paper

A study on psychological well-being of final year management students during COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in India

Dr. Biswajit Satpathy^{1*}, Esrafil Ali²

ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the anxiety, depression and stress level of students during COVID-19 outbreak. The online questionnaire surveyed 80 students from the 250 population of MBA in Western Odisha, India. Two steps analysis have been done using EXCEL and MAXQDA software. The data collected were inserted in EXCEL and were analyzed by descriptive statistics (frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation) for the DASS21 questionnaire. Content analysis for open ended questions was carried out with the help of MAXQDA Software. The inferential statistics suggests that the level of depression was as high as 43% among the students (Mean 8.7, SD 6.047073). The main reasons for depressions among students are mental tension, career and negative psychology (maximum hits ranging 80%) and also other factors such as economic downturn, financial issues, future life, social distress, satisfaction in life, and job offers revoked (hits ranging from 73-46% observed) as revealed by Content Analysis. The institutions should adopt an online method of psychosocial intervention to reduce the depression level of the students.

Keywords: *Mental wellbeing, COVID-19, DASS21, Content Analysis*

Coronavirus (COVID-19) is a pandemic associated with severe respiratory syndrome. It originated from Wuhan, China, in December 2019. The World Health Organization (WHO) on 30th January 2020 showed concern for this disease and affirmed it as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern and on 11th March 2020 accepted this as a pandemic. The ongoing pandemic COVID-19 has been announced by the World Health Organization as the sixth public health emergency of international concern. In December 2019 in China Coronavirus was first spotted. People suffering from Corona show symptoms of fever, dry coughing and breathlessness (Guan et al. 2020 and Holshue et al. 2020). Million cases of COVID-19 have been reported throughout the world resulting in more than 170,000 deaths. As the numbers of cases are increasing in different countries around the world, the anxiety symptoms are also rising among the communities.

¹ Professor, Department of Business Administration, Sambalpur University, JyotiVihar, Burla , Sambalpur, Odisha, India

² Research Scholar, Department of Business Administration, Sambalpur University, JyotiVihar, Burla , Sambalpur, Odisha, India

**Responding Author*

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Anxiety levels will definitely rise but the question is how to manage this stress before it becomes devastating. It is quite natural that people will go through great stress and bigger anxiety symptoms due to this pandemic. General public is frightened and there is fear among the mass relating to their health and wellbeing of their loved ones, economic downturn and uncertainty about the future. The media coverage is also feeding to the anxiety levels. Quarantine and social isolation can add to the stress and anxiety levels and may lead to increase one's signs of depression.

Studies conducted on the impact of quarantine and social isolation after the outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in 2003 and 2014. Ebola outbreak has reported negative psychological effects on the mass including post-traumatic stress symptoms, confusion, and anger. The stressors after long quarantine duration are mostly fears of infection, frustration, boredom, inadequate supplies, inadequate information, financial loss, and stigma.

A comparative study by Wang et al. (2011) on undergraduate students who were quarantined with those not quarantined reported that there exists no significant difference between the two groups with respect to general mental health problems. Since the study only took the young students population perhaps the result reported came out to be such due to the fact that young people generally have less responsibilities than adults and therefore this conclusion cannot be generalised.

Rubin (2020) writes that the profits of compulsory mass quarantine need to be evaluated cautiously against the psychological costs. As far as possible, the use of quarantine and lockdown as measures to protect the public health should be reduced, as there are negative consequences associated with it.

Review of literature shows that the psychological shock of quarantine is extensive, considerable, and long-term in nature. Quarantine and lockdown of the general mass should be used in extreme conditions. On the other hand, the psychological outcomes of not using quarantine and lockdown and allowing the disease to infect the mass might be worse (Hull 2005). So it requires a judicious decision before implementing such measures weighing both the pros and cons because withdrawing liberty for the wider public good is often a debatable issue. If quarantine and lockdown is essential, steps should be taken to ensure that this is bearable for the mass.

Studies on the disaster mental health have reported on the results of traumatic and post-traumatic stress disorders on communities. Recently some studies have been conducted to extend the positive view on mental health (Herrman 2012; Wade et al. 2012). The approach is to bring people from illness to a normal state, and to make them powerful to achieve a positive level of mental health (Seligman 2011).

Epidemic outbreaks generate numerous challenges in bring back good health in between the beginning of an infection and healing. There exists a long-term internal suffering of families of those who have seen death in their family due to the disease and they demonstrate a mental "iceberg effect." In the individual level, pandemic causes vulnerabilities, social stigma, distress, and isolation and the individuals may experience fear, anxiousness, numbness, and detachment. On a community level, the whole community can experience fear and isolation during and after an infectious disease pandemic. This has been seen during the 2009–2010

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H1N1 influenza pandemic. Individuals of USA experienced confusion, anxiety, and increased risky behaviours like smoking, drinking, drug misuse, recklessness, and unsafe work practices because of a sense of uncertainty. There were concern about the availability of medicines, shortages of workforce, and strategies to lessen the problem (Pfefferbaum et al. 2012). Public health workers and their families too experience some of these mental health issues.

This new pandemic COVID-19 is causing anxiety because of its instantaneous nature of transmission, its mortality statistics, its overestimation by the infected, uncertainty about the future, the economic affects, the distrust of adequate prevention of the disease and necessary availability of health care facilities. Anxiety affects the immune system and thus the risk of the virus infection increases. Public's anxious reactions gives rise to public disruptive behaviors such as people rushing to stores, health care centers, medicine stores, and therefore health care service system gets affected (WHO 2020).

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND STUDENT'S MENTAL WELL-BEING

During our literature review we have come across very little number of researches on the mental well- being of students during a pandemic. Desai (2020) write about the anxiety among the American students reports that for low-income students, the closer of the colleges because of COVID-19 is not a matter of rejoice, they said, "It's been really chaotic". The uncertainty of getting the degree is a matter of concern for many students. Colleges in US have sent all their students home for the rest of the year. Shutting down a campus is a setback in career for most of the students and they term this closure as a fire-alarm for their career. Students from reputed institutions like Harvard may be able to deal with the financial and academic fallout of a pandemic-triggered school shutdown, but many students elsewhere aren't at all prepared to absorb the shock. Many students do not have reliable internet access for online classes. In India too, all the academic institutions have been closed down. In this present scenario, the anxiety among the students is rising. Due to coronavirus pandemic, students and faculty members are facing stress caused due to the disturbance in their personal and work lives. To cope up in such a public health crisis and to maintain sound mental health, both the students and the teachers are to rely on each other. In this study, we aim to assess the anxiety, depression and stress level of Indian students during COVID-19 outbreak and the reasons for such fear and anxiety.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design and sampling

The study was an online survey conducted among the post graduate level final year students of management studies (MBA Students) conducted in Western Odisha, India. There were around 100 students in total enrolled in a premier central government institution in this part of the country. The students from this institution were chosen on the basis of their final campus placement for jobs and reliable internet availability at their home. Since the campuses are locked down the students are available in their home, convenient sampling was done on the basis of reliable internet access available to the students. 90 students were sent the questionnaire and out of them 83 responded. 3 responses were incomplete so they were not included. The sample size required with a margin of error 5% and confidence level 95% was 80. Thus, we calculated the results with 80 responses only.

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Data collection tools

DASS21 questionnaire was applied to collect the data to assess the Depression, Anxiety and Stress level of the students. The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 Items (DASS-21) is a set of three self-report scales designed to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress developed by Lovibond, S.H. & Lovibond, P.F. (1995). The questionnaire was obtained from the Manual for the Depression Anxiety & Stress Scales (2nd Ed.) Sydney: Psychology Foundation. A set of eight open ended questions were also developed to find out the reasons for their Depression, Anxiety & Stress. The validity and reliability of the DASS21 questionnaire have been confirmed by national and international studies. The Cronbach's alpha was also calculated using SPSS for three subscales which shows 0.740 for anxiety, 0.812 for depression and 0.785 for stress subscale. Thus, the Alpha coefficients for all the subscales (depression, anxiety and stress) are acceptable in the present research and there exists internal consistency of the subscales.

The DASS21 questionnaire which assessed autonomic arousal, skeletal muscle effects, situational anxiety and subjective experience of anxious impact was reported by the students. They were made aware of the prevailing situation due to Corona pandemic. Secondly, the researchers also used eight open ended questions to collect the comprehensive views of students on the Covid 19 pandemic situations and how it had impacted on them during the lockdown.

The data collection process took 10 days (5th April 2020 to 15th April 2020). At the beginning of the online survey, a full explanation on the purpose of the study was intimated to the students and their consent to participate in the study was obtained. The questionnaire was designed using Google form and the students were shared a link created to take part in the survey. All the closed ended and open ended questions were fed into the forms for the survey purpose. Students were also requested to fill the survey questionnaires through a separate mail.

Data analysis method

We used two step analysis using Excel and MAXQDA software. The quantitative data collected were inserted in EXCEL and were analyzed by descriptive statistics (frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation) for the DASS21 questionnaire. The Content analysis for open ended questions was carried out with the help of MAXQDA Software. All the responses were first arranged in excel file in supporting format and imported in the software. The codification was done with the help of intuition and judgments. The various thematic and systematic codes were generated for the analysis purpose. Further, all the responses were retrieved into the segments using category wise survey responses. All the outputs were exported using excel file and interpretation was done.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Depression, Anxiety and Stress Measurement (DASS Analysis)

Quantitative Analysis

From the **Table I** illustrated below, it is indicated that the depression level among students was normal (57%), Mild (23%), Moderate (14%) and Severe (6%). Besides, the analysis also indicates that the Anxiety level was noted as Normal (84%), Mild (6%) and Moderate (10%). The results also demonstrate that the Stress level was 89% normal and 11% mild among the students. As shown in the table, it is observed that the depression level was recorded high

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(43% falls under the range of mild, moderate and severe) among students compared to anxiety and stress.

Table I: Level of Depression, Anxiety and Stress in Students				
Depression Level among Students during Covid Pandemic				
Severe	5	6%	Mean	8.7
Moderate	11	14%	SD	6.047073
Mild	18	23%		
Normal	46	57%		
N	80	100%		
Anxiety Level among Students during Covid Pandemic				
Severe	0	0%	Mean	3.95
Moderate	8	10%	SD	3.987004
Mild	5	6%		
Normal	67	84%		
N	80	100%		
Stress Level among Students during Covid Pandemic				
Mild	9	11%	Mean	7.525
Normal	71	89%	SD	4.701131
N	0	0%		
Source: Developed for Research by Authors				

Graph 1: The Graph showing the level of depression among students

Graph 2: The Graph showing the level of Anxiety among students

Graph 3: The Graph showing the level of Stress among students

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS RESPONSES

Qualitative Analysis

SPREAD OF CORONAVIRUS (COVID 19) AND ITS IMPACT ON STUDENTS MENTAL STATUS

From the Content analysis of the responses collected from students, it is indicated that most of the students were feeling tensed and pressurised due to the adverse situation of COVID 19. The reasons behind the same were being observed as slowdown economy, career path, family problems, lockdown situation, home quarantine, losing of job, job crisis, pandemic environment in the country, spread of rumours etc. Please refer **Table II**.

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Table II: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of students mental health		
Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP01	None	
RESP02	Career growth in economic slowdown	Slowdown, Career path
RESP03	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP04	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP05	No mental pressure for any impact on me personally. I am just worried for the future consequences of this pandemic. Like in job life, economy of the country, impact on poor etc.	Pandemic, Job
RESP06	While thinking about the impact of COVID-19 on the less fortunate, driving millions back to poverty, I feel like I need to do something but I don't know where to start, so I feel lost and a bit tensed.	
RESP07	Losing job	Job
RESP08	Worried about career progression	Career path
RESP09	Career growth in economic slowdown	Slowdown, Career path
RESP10	No idea	
RESP11	Career growth in economic slowdown	Slowdown, Career path
RESP12	Just concerned about my campus job offer security	Job
RESP13	No major tension	
RESP14	Rumours, negative news/information, spread of incorrect information create the mental pressure	
RESP15	Fear of job crisis	Job
RESP16	Spread of virus is very pandemic. Just to buy some necessary items also some time I get tensed and helping some people also makes me tensed.	Pandemic
RESP17	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP18	I want to leave	
RESP19	Pandemic situation may result some losses	Pandemic
RESP20	Job Loss	Job
RESP21	Fear of job	Job
RESP22	None	
RESP23	None	
RESP24	None	
RESP25	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP26	Career growth in economic slowdown	Slowdown, Career path
RESP27	No idea	
RESP28	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP29	Not facing any challenge	
RESP30	No Opinion	
RESP31	Career on stake	Career path
RESP32	No idea	
RESP33	Career growth in economic slowdown	Slowdown, Career path
RESP34	None	
RESP35	No idea	
RESP36	Go home feeling	Home
RESP37	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP38	No idea	
RESP39	None	

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Table II: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of students mental health		
Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP40	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP41	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP42	No idea	
RESP43	None	
RESP44	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP45	None	
RESP46	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP47	None	
RESP48	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP49	In this lockdown.. I want to go home	Lockdown, Home
RESP50	None	
RESP51	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP52	None	
RESP53	None	
RESP54	None	
RESP55	None	
RESP56	None	
RESP57	None	
RESP58	None	
RESP59	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP60	None	
RESP61	None	
RESP62	None	
RESP63	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP64	None	
RESP65	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP66	None	
RESP67	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP68	None	
RESP69	None	
RESP70	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP71	As of now am not facing anything like that	
RESP72	None	
RESP73	None	
RESP74	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP75	None	
RESP76	None	
RESP77	No idea	
RESP78	it should not spread to my family	Family
RESP79	None	
RESP80	As of now am not facing anything like that	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

STUDENTS CAREER AND OUTBREAK OF COVID 19

Most of the students were worried about their offers from companies. They were tensed because they were feeling insecure if they could be able to join the company and if yes, that may get affected due to economic slowdown. The common reasons of worries among students were job opportunities, delay in joining companies, coronavirus, and delay in start of career. **Table III** shows the results.

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Table III: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of students career

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP01	No	
RESP02	yes, less opportunity and more demand	Opportunity
RESP03	Not at all	
RESP04	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP05	Covid 19	
RESP06	Covid 19	Covid
RESP07	Yes. The company rescinded my job offer	
RESP08	Yes. My final placement offer has been rescinded by the company due to Covid-19	Covid
RESP09	yes, less opportunity and more demand	Opportunity
RESP10	No danger now	
RESP11	yes, less opportunity and more demand	Opportunity
RESP12	Because I am not sure when I ll be able to join and that too if my offer is not rescinded. And if it is rescind, then i ll have to start at a very low pay, making no sense of doing this mba after two years of workex	
RESP13	Yes... Job offers may be revoked as companies are facing losses	
RESP14	No, I am not feeling unsecured about my career.	
RESP15	yes, fear of losing/not getting job in a depressing economy	
RESP16	Yes, as many companies are revoking the offer letters	
RESP17	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP18	No danger now	
RESP19	Companies may withdraw job	
RESP20	Companies may not take us	
RESP21	Fear of jon loss	
RESP22	No	
RESP23	No	
RESP24	No	
RESP25	Not at all	
RESP26	yes, less opportunity and more demand	Opportunity
RESP27	No danger now	
RESP28	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP29	Not at all	
RESP30	No issue	
RESP31	Less market opportunity	Opportunity
RESP32	No danger now	
RESP33	yes, less opportunity and more demand	Opportunity
RESP34	No	
RESP35	No danger now	
RESP36	Waiting for normal situation	
RESP37	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP38	No danger now	
RESP39	No	

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Table III: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of students career

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP40	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP41	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP42	No danger now	
RESP43	No	
RESP44	Not at all	
RESP45	No	
RESP46	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP47	No	
RESP48	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP49	No, Opportunities might get delayed due to COVID-19, but things may get back to normal	Covid, Delay Career
RESP50	No	
RESP51	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP52	No	
RESP53	No	
RESP54	No	
RESP55	No	
RESP56	No	
RESP57	No	
RESP58	No	
RESP59	Not at all	
RESP60	No	
RESP61	No	
RESP62	No	
RESP63	Not at all	
RESP64	No	
RESP65	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP66	No	
RESP67	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP68	No	
RESP69	No	
RESP70	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP71	Not at all	
RESP72	No	
RESP73	No	
RESP74	Yes, as most of the joining are delayed and some offers are getting cancelled	Joining, Delay Career
RESP75	No	
RESP76	No	
RESP77	No danger now	
RESP78	Joining late	Joining
RESP79	No	

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Table III: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of students career

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP80	Not at all	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

COVID 19 PANDEMIC AND FINANCIAL TROUBLE IN STUDENT'S LIFE

From the analysis, it is interpreted that most of the student's issues were their timely joining in the company which may certainly impact their financial earnings. Further, it is also interpreted that they faced challenges in repaying their loan amounts to banks because of their uncertain financial conditions of job. **Table IV** depicts the reasons of their financial burdens.

Table IV: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of financial matters

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP01	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP02	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment
RESP03	Nope	
RESP04	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP05	It may create. As I told, I may be earning lesser than what i should have because of sloe down of economies and markets. Definitely, my financial conditions will be impacted.	Earnings
RESP06	Cannot say for sure but I have an educational loan which I intent to payoff as early as possible, this won't be possible if I don't have a job.	Loan repayment
RESP07	I don't know	
RESP08	Yes. Uncertainty about career might create monetary difficulties.	
RESP09	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment
RESP10	May get some	
RESP11	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment
RESP12	No as of now	
RESP13	Maybe	
RESP14	No.	
RESP15	Not as of now.	
RESP16	No	
RESP18	many face problems	
RESP19	As of now no	
RESP20	No idea	
RESP21	No	
RESP22	Late appointment	
RESP23	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP24	Late appointment	
RESP25	Nope	
RESP26	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment
RESP27	May get some	
RESP29	Nope	
RESP30	May get some	
RESP31	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment
RESP32	May get some	
RESP33	Education loan repayments	Loan repayment

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Table IV: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of financial matters

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP34	Late appointment	
RESP35	May get some	
RESP38	May get some	
RESP39	Late appointment	
RESP40	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP42	May get some	
RESP43	Late appointment	
RESP44	Nope	
RESP45	Late appointment	
RESP46	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP47	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP50	Late appointment	
RESP51	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP52	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP53	Late appointment	
RESP54	Late appointment	
RESP55	Late appointment	
RESP56	Late appointment	
RESP57	Late appointment	
RESP58	Late appointment	
RESP59	Nope	
RESP60	Late appointment	
RESP61	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP62	Late appointment	
RESP63	Nope	
RESP64	Late appointment	
RESP65	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP66	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP67	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP68	appointment	
RESP69	No appointment	
RESP70	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP71	Nope	
RESP72	Late appointment	
RESP73	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP74	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP75	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP76	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining
RESP77	May get some	
RESP78	Yes, I have education loan and getting a good paying job would help me in getting the loan repayment started	Loan repayment
RESP79	Yes. Late joining to new company.	Joining

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Table IV: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of financial matters

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP80	Nope	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

COMPANIES LAYOFF JOBS, ECONOMIC DOWNTURN DUE TO COVID 19 AND STUDENT'S SITUATIONS

Due to the adverse impact of covid on economy, most of the companies are planning to lay off their employees for certain period of time. This has posed serious threats on the career of the students who may recently join the companies. From the study, it was found that students were in mental tension, anxiety and stress due to the reasons that they could be unemployed and economic downturn may result into job insecurity in future, their offers may be revoked, etc. **Table V** illustrates the same.

Table V: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of economic downturn and jobs

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP01	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP02	Sitting unemployed for a long time or getting settled where you don not want to	Unemployment Situation
RESP03	Very bad	
RESP04	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP05	Insecurities due to uncertainty of job. I will think about lay off during working which may impact my work.	
RESP06	It puts me under a lot of stress, I can't think straight sometimes.	
RESP07	Nothing	
RESP08	Although I was yet to join the company, but my offer was rescinded. It must very difficult for people who have lost their existing jobs to cope with this as it is very important to have sufficient funds at a time like this.	Offer revoked
RESP09	Sitting unemployed for a long time or getting settled where you don not want to	Unemployment Situation
RESP10	May Get some	
RESP11	Sitting unemployed for a long time or getting settled where you don not want to	Unemployment Situation
RESP12	I am not sure when I ll be able to join and that too if my offer is not rescinded. And if it is rescind, then i ll have to start at a very low pay, making no sense of doing this mba after two years of workex	Offer revoked
RESP13	Emotional and mental stress	
RESP14	It creates a need of excelling at the work domain and focus on learning and being adaptive to situation.	
RESP15	Financial insecurity. Fear of not being able to be financially independent.	
RESP16	As iam a fresher getting job would be difficult again to get in to corporate office.	
RESP18	Nothing	
RESP19	Financial Issues may create	
RESP20	Nothing	
RESP21	Fear of not being able to be financially strong	
RESP22	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP23	May not get offer	Offer revoked

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Table V: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of economic downturn and jobs		
Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP24	Offer revoked	Offer revoked
RESP25	Very bad	
RESP26	Sitting unemployed for a long time or getting settled where you don not want to	Unemployment Situation
RESP27	May Get some	
RESP29	Very bad	
RESP30	May Get some	
RESP31	Unemployment is the challenge	
RESP32	May Get some	
RESP33	Sitting unemployed for a long time or getting settled where you don not want to	Unemployment Situation
RESP34	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP35	May Get some	
RESP38	May Get some	
RESP39	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP40	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP42	May Get some	
RESP43	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP44	Very bad	
RESP45	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP46	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP47	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP50	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP51	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP52	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP53	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP54	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP55	No offer then issues	Offer revoked
RESP56	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP57	Job	
RESP58	Job	
RESP59	Very bad	
RESP60	offer is also revoked. Then	Offer revoked
RESP61	Company may not give job	
RESP62	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP63	Very bad	
RESP64	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP65	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP66	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP67	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP68	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP69	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP70	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP71	Very bad	
RESP72	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked

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Table V: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of economic downturn and jobs

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP73	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP74	I am in start of my career and this situation is really bad for us, as we are about to join the workforce	
RESP75	Very bad situation	
RESP76	Very bad situation	
RESP77	May Get some	
RESP78	May effect my early career s	
RESP79	What if my offer is also revoked.	Offer revoked
RESP80	Very bad	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

COVID 19 UNCERTAINTIES SURROUNDINGS AND PSYCHOSOCIAL EFFECTS ON STUDENTS SUCH AS STRESS, IRRITABILITY, FEAR, CONFUSION, ANGER, BOREDOM, DEPRESSION, ANXIETY, INSOMNIA, ETC

It is interpreted from the responses that few students were suffering from insomnia, stress, boredom, anxiety and depression due to the prevailing situation of lockdown and pandemic. Some were neutral having no influence on them. **Table VI** shows the results.

Table VI: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of psychological feelings of students

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP01	No	
RESP02	stress, fear	Stress
RESP03	Not at all	
RESP04	No	
RESP05	No, I am stable currently until this point of time.	
RESP06	Sometimes I feel anxious, I fear the uncertainty and I might be suffering from Insomnia	Insomnia
RESP07	Yes	
RESP08	Yes. Confusion, boredom, anxiety.	Anxiety, Boredom
RESP09	stress, fear	Stress
RESP10	NO	
RESP11	stress, fear	Stress
RESP12	A bit of stress and insomnia	Insomnia, Stress
RESP13	Yes.. Anxiety	Anxiety
RESP14	No, I'm not.	
RESP15	Anxiety of what will happen to the job market.	Anxiety
RESP16	No	
RESP17	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP18	Monotony and boredom	Boredom
RESP19	Yes	
RESP20	Yes	
RESP21	Anxiety of what will happen to the job market.	Anxiety
RESP22	No	
RESP23	No	
RESP24	No	
RESP25	Not at all	
RESP26	stress, fear	Stress
RESP27	NO	

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Table VI: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of psychological feelings of students		
Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP28	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP29	Not at all	
RESP30	NO	
RESP31	stress, fear	Stress
RESP32	NO	
RESP33	stress, fear	Stress
RESP34	No	
RESP35	NO	
RESP36	Stress	Stress
RESP37	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP38	NO	
RESP39	No	
RESP40	No	
RESP41	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP42	NO	
RESP43	No	
RESP44	Not at all	
RESP45	No	
RESP46	No	
RESP47	No	
RESP48	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP49	Yes,sometime boredom and stress due to no jobs available in the market	Boredom, Stress
RESP50	No	
RESP51	No	
RESP52	No	
RESP53	No	
RESP54	No	
RESP55	No	
RESP56	No	
RESP57	No	
RESP58	No	
RESP59	Not at all	
RESP60	No	
RESP61	No	
RESP62	No	
RESP63	Not at all	
RESP64	No	
RESP65	No	
RESP66	No	
RESP67	No	
RESP68	No	
RESP69	No	
RESP70	No	
RESP71	Not at all	
RESP72	No	
RESP73	No	
RESP74	No	

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Table VI: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact of psychological feelings of students

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP75	No	
RESP76	No	
RESP77	NO	
RESP78	No	
RESP79	No	
RESP80	Not at all	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

HOME CONFINEMENT AND PSYCHOLOGICAL/SOCIAL DISTRESS IN STUDENTS

Table VII indicated the impact of lockdown and home quarantine on students' life. The study explored the main factors as family association during this turbulent time. The family was focused more. Students valued family more than jobs and career in the present situation.

Table VII: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on social stress of students

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP02	yes, but it may create new avenues and a new way of work and life style	
RESP03	It won't happen	
RESP04	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP05	Personally, I don't have much issues with this. I am getting a lot of time for myself to introspect myself and plan my life forward.this time won't comr again.	
RESP06	I am not sure about psychological but definitely social distress	
RESP07	1	
RESP08	It is important to discuss it with your loved ones. Also important to accept that the entire humanity is going through this. Accept it as a part of life and keep fighting.	
RESP09	yes, but it may create new avenues and a new way of work and life style	
RESP10	No	
RESP11	yes, but it may create new avenues and a new way of work and life style	
RESP12	If it continues for a longer time, then maybe Yes	
RESP13	Yes it does	
RESP14	Being aware about the situation and researching about mental health helps	
RESP15	May result in anxiety due to uncertainty of the situation.	
RESP16	Stay home and be tension free	
RESP18	May arise anxiety and stress	
RESP19	Stay home	
RESP20	May be	
RESP21	May result in Stress due to uncertainty	
RESP23	No	
RESP24	No	
RESP25	It won't happen	
RESP26	yes, but it may create new avenues and a new way of work and life style	
RESP27	No	

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Table VII: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on social stress of students

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP29	It won't happen	
RESP30	No	
RESP31	Yes it does	
RESP32	No	
RESP33	yes, but it may create new avenues and a new way of work and life style	
RESP35	No	
RESP38	No	
RESP40	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP42	No	
RESP44	It won't happen	
RESP46	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP51	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP59	It won't happen	
RESP63	It won't happen	
RESP65	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP67	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP70	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP71	It won't happen	
RESP74	It may affect most of people but spending time with family and trying to get engage in your hobbies can help	Family
RESP77	No	
RESP78	Family effect	Family
RESP80	It won't happen	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

COVID 19 AND STUDENTS LIFE SATISFACTION

Table VIII indicates that most of the students were satisfied to the lower extent due to this pandemic of coronavirus. However, it is also pertinent to note that some were satisfied as of the present situation as they were waiting for normal conditions after the lockdown.

Table VIII: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on students life

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP03	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP04	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP05	7/10 .	
RESP06	On a scale of 1 to 10 with 1 being not satisfied at all and 10 being completely satisfied I would say 3.	Satisfied
RESP07	Not very satisfied	Satisfied
RESP08	Not a lot. There has been a lack of motivation and lack of willingness to do things.	
RESP10	No	
RESP12	6/10 because i am getting time to spend with my family Which we generally do not get that easily	

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Table VIII: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on students life

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP13	Not ver satisfied	Satisfied
RESP14	I'm satisfied with the time I'm utilising to acquire new skills and being optimistic about future	Satisfied
RESP15	Not at all.	
RESP16	30% satisfied as I am getting time to work on my weakness	Satisfied
RESP18	No motivation	
RESP19	No statisfied	
RESP20	Not very satisfied	Satisfied
RESP21	No	
RESP23	No	
RESP24	No	
RESP25	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP27	No	
RESP29	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP30	No	
RESP32	No	
RESP35	No	
RESP38	No	
RESP40	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP42	No	
RESP44	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP46	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP51	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP53	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP59	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP63	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP65	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP67	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP70	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP71	Well satisfied	Satisfied
RESP74	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP77	No	
RESP78	Somewhat satisfied but still want these days to end soon	Satisfied
RESP80	Well satisfied	Satisfied

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

MAJOR PROBLEMS OF COVID ON STUDENTS' FUTURE LIFE

The major issues indicated by students were job packages, job related issues, financial crisis, uncertainty in job market and financial crisis in future time to come. Students were feeling insecure and inconsistent in terms of their personal development.

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Table IX: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on students future life

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP02	Difficult to assess now	
RESP03	Not much	
RESP04	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issues, Financial Crisis
RESP05	Career wise it may slow down my growth rate. Apart from that, things will settle down with time gradually.	
RESP06	Job uncertainty, financial insecurity, inconsistent personal development	Uncertainty, Financial Crisis
RESP07	I don't know	
RESP08	The world is going to change because of Covid 19. Once we get through this, nothing is going to be the same. We humans as a whole will always have to be careful and prepared for uncertainties.	
RESP09	Difficult to assess now	
RESP10	No opinion	
RESP11	Difficult to assess now	
RESP12	Just the career and travelling	
RESP13	Job uncertainty	
RESP14	Limited access to the public places and limited travel.	
RESP15	Financial uncertainty. Decrement in social skills.	Uncertainty, Financial Crisis
RESP16	We feel uncomfortable still in large gatherings	
RESP18	Still wait and watch	
RESP19	Feeling worried	
RESP20	No opinion	
RESP21	Financial uncertainty.	Uncertainty, Financial Crisis
RESP23	No	
RESP24	No	
RESP25	Not much	
RESP26	Difficult to assess now	
RESP27	No opinion	
RESP29	Not much	
RESP30	No opinion	
RESP31	Difficult to assess now	
RESP32	No opinion	
RESP33	Difficult to assess now	
RESP35	No opinion	
RESP38	No opinion	
RESP40	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issues, Financial Crisis
RESP42	No opinion	
RESP44	Not much	
RESP46	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issues, Financial Crisis

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Table IX: Theme: Covid 19 pandemic and its impact on students future life

Respondents	Responses	Major Factors Indicated
RESP51	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP56	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP59	Not much	
RESP63	Not much	
RESP65	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP67	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP70	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP71	Not much	
RESP74	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP77	No opinion	
RESP78	Jobs and package offered will be low due to pandemic and financial crisis	Package, Job related issued, Financial Crisis
RESP80	Not much	

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

MAJOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS LIFE DURING COVID 19 AND LOCKDOWN

From the below Table X, it is indicated that Job Offers, Loan repayment, delay in career start, stress situation, financial crisis, joining in companies, family were major problems among students in Covid 19 pandemic. Besides, the table also shows that mental tension, career and negative psychology were the major factors to be emphasized upon among students issues and problems. (maximum hits ranging 80%). Further, the factors such as economic downturn, financial issues, future life, social distress, satisfaction in life, and job offers revoked are also to be addressed (hits ranging from 73-46% observed).

Table X: Level of Frequencies of factors affecting students Depression, Anxiety and Stress

Factors	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Mental status	80	100.00	100.00
Career	80	100.00	100.00
Psychological Effects	80	100.00	100.00
Economic Downturn	73	91.25	91.25
Financial Issues	73	91.25	91.25
Future Life	47	58.75	58.75
Social Distress	46	57.50	57.50
Satisfaction in Life	41	51.25	51.25
Offer revoked	25	31.25	31.25
Satisfied	24	30.00	30.00
Loan repayment	16	20.00	20.00
Delay Career	14	17.50	17.50
Stress	14	17.50	17.50
Financial Crisis	13	16.25	16.25
Joining	10	12.50	12.50
Job related issued	10	12.50	12.50

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Table X: Level of Frequencies of factors affecting students Depression, Anxiety and Stress

Factors	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage (valid)
Package	10	12.50	12.50
Family	9	11.25	11.25
Joining	9	11.25	11.25
Family	9	11.25	11.25
Covid	8	10.00	10.00
Boredom	8	10.00	10.00
Career path	7	8.75	8.75
Home	7	8.75	8.75
Lockdown	6	7.50	7.50
Opportunity	6	7.50	7.50
Job	6	7.50	7.50
Unemployment Situation	5	6.25	6.25
Slowdown	5	6.25	6.25
Anxiety	4	5.00	5.00
Pandemic	3	3.75	3.75
Uncertainty	3	3.75	3.75
Insomnia	2	2.50	2.50
Earnings	1	1.25	1.25

Source: Data Interpretation result output from MAXQDA Software

Graph 4: Students Responses Records during Covid 19 Pandemic

Students Responses Records during Covid 19 Pandemic and Lockdown

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the present study was to evaluate the level of anxiety, depression and stress among the MBA students during the outbreak of coronavirus. The findings of the present study indicate that approximately 43% students are in depressions, 16% of students have experienced anxiety and 11% stresses. The main reasons for depressions are due to mental

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tension, career issues and negative psychology (maximum hits upto 80% noted) and also other factors such as economic downturn, financial issues, future life, social distress, satisfaction in life, and job offers revoked (hits ranging from 73-46% were observed).

Recently researchers Zandifar A., Badrfam R (2020), have emphasized on paying special attention to providing psychosocial care during COVID-19 prevalence and the findings of the present study also emphasizes on the necessity of the provision of such services by the institutions to the students by establishing a student online counselling committee comprising of the head of the institution, faculty members, sociologists and clinical psychologists.

A study by Wang et al. (2020) showed that more than a quarter of participants experienced moderate to severe anxiety symptoms, and women suffered from psychological distress and stress, anxiety, and depression. The findings of the present study show that depression level is significantly high 43%, which may be due to concern about future and economic consequences. Students are the future active economic work force of the society and they are mostly affected by unemployment, inflation, and business closures due to such events.

Over flooding of news broadcast on COVID-19 is mostly disappointing and frustrating and sometimes rumours comes in social media, therefore when someone is constantly exposed to COVID-19 news, the level of anxiety goes higher. The hotline services are set up by government to offer COVID related services. The decision makers are mainly concerned with reducing the spread of the disease and also there exists a shortage of workforce for psycho-social counseling so we find that emphasis on mental wellbeing of the populace has taken the second bench. Low and middle income countries face difficulties in providing online mental health services due to lack of proper access to the disadvantaged classes and doubts the usefulness of online psychological interventions. This is due to the fact that a very few number of researches have been conducted to confirm these services (Yao et al. 2020)

Coronavirus infection does not differentiate between geography, ethnicity, religion and politics, therefore it is considered as a global issue and pandemic. Earlier research shows that people who regularly follow COVID-19 news experience more anxiety, depression and stress than who regularly do not follow the news. Mental health professionals, NGOs have major role to educate the public about common adverse psychological consequences, promote healthy behaviours, advice people to lower their exposure to negative news, and to prevent social isolation, use alternative ways of communication such as virtual networks during the pandemic. (Banerjee 2020)

The study was conducted under the COVID-19 pandemic circumstances and during the lockdown period in India, so self-quarantine was recommended as the safest way to stay healthy, therefore conducting online research was completely safe. An acceptable number of sample size participated in the study, so our findings can be considered highly valid. The less number of questions in the questionnaire was a motivational factor for which the respondents were more willing to answer the questions. The answers are self-reporting and the survey was conducted without a control group and above all the study has been carried out in a very small geographical part of India therefore the results cannot be generalized.

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Conflict of Interest

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